

PIACERE

Deliverable D5.8

IOP prototype – v2

DRAFT

Editor(s):	Eneko Osaba, Iñaki Etxaniz, Gorka Benguria
Responsible Partner:	TECNALIA
Status-Version:	Final-v1.0
Date:	25.11.2022
Distribution level (CO, PU):	PU

Project Number:	101000162
Project Title:	PIACERE

Title of Deliverable:	IOP prototype – v2
Due Date of Delivery to the EC	30.11.2022

Workpackage responsible for the Deliverable:	WP5 - Package, release and configure Infrastructure as Code
Editor(s):	Eneko Osaba (TECNALIA)
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Recommended/mandatory readers:	WP3, WP5, WP6

Abstract:	The main outcome of T5.3 from M1 to M30 will be presented in this deliverable. Each deliverable will have a Technical Specification Report and a software prototype [KR9], including the explanation of the algorithms
Keyword List:	IOP, Catalogue of Infrastructural Elements, Optimization, Multi-Objective Algorithm.
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Document Description

Version	Date	Modifications Introduced	
		Modification Reason	Modified by
v0.1	01.10.2022	First TOC and sections assignment	TECNALIA
v0.2	16.11.2022	IOP and IEC new versions described	TECNALIA
V0.3	21.11.2022	Internally reviewed version	POLIMI
V0.4	22.11.2022	Reviewer comments addressed	TECNALIA
V1.0	25.11.2022	Ready for submission	TECNALIA

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Terms and abbreviations

CSP	Cloud Service Provider
DevOps	Development and Operation
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
IaC	Infrastructure as Code
IEP	IaC execution platform
IOP	IaC Optimization
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
SW	Software
IEC	Infrastructural Elements Catalogue
KR	Key Result
SOA	Service Oriented Architecture
REST	Representational State Transfer
OAS	Open API Specification
API	Application Programming Interface
JWT	Java Web Token

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Executive Summary

This document contains the technical description of the second version of the Infrastructure Optimization Platform (IOP) [KR9] developed in the context of PIACERE. In the specific context of this project, the optimization problem modelled has the main objective of finding the best combination of infrastructural and resource configuration to optimally deploy a service, considering the existence of an Infrastructural Elements Catalogue (IEC). The outcome of the IOP depends on the infrastructural elements that comprise the service and the Functional and Non-Functional Requirements introduced by the user, which are gathered by the IOP through the input DOML model.

Along with the functional and technical description of both the IOP Optimizer and IEC, this deliverable also includes different sections around the installation and usage of this second IOP version. Also, this document introduces the instructions that should be followed for testing the developed software.

Furthermore, the IOP architecture and the general design of it are also presented in this deliverable, so that it allows the comparison of the several tool versions and the evolution of the complete IOP. The general requirements and the functionalities are also described in this document, as well as the coverage provided by this M24 tool, which is the original subject of the document.

In a nutshell, the main work conducted among M12 and M24 has been focused on the adaptation of the IOP first prototype, which was clearly an academic-oriented prototype, to the use-case oriented version of the IOP described in this document. This mature version of the IOP is DOML compliant, and it is able to attend the user needs, providing optimized solutions based on user's requirements. Thanks to the work conducted on this second year of the project, the integration of the IOP into the PIACERE IDE has been already done, and it has also been preliminarily tested on use cases, providing a satisfactory performance.

Next (and last) version of this document (which is planned to be ready in M30, D5.9) will present the evolution of the IOP tool, the new features that the third release will provide to the developer and the technical characteristics associated to it.

1 Introduction

1.1 About this deliverable

This document represents the second version of the *IOP Prototype* deliverable, which is part of the work done in WP5 - *Package, release and configure Infrastructure as code*. Thus, the main goal of this deliverable is to describe the main advancements conducted over the first prototypes developed in M12 on the IEC and the IOP Optimizer. As explained, these advancements are focused on the transformation of the IOP from an academic-oriented prototype to a use-case oriented tool. This document describes different aspects around these components such as technical description, implementation, and installation of both IEC and the optimization engine.

1.2 Document structure

This manuscript is composed of 8 sections. Section 2 is devoted to providing a general description of the work performed on the topics dealt in this deliverable. Sections 3 and 4 delve into the implementations of both IEC and IOP Optimizer. The following Sections 5, 6 and 7 are devoted to detail the delivery and usage of both components. Finally, Section 8 presents the conclusions and the future steps until the end of the project.

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2 Best configuration deployments based on optimization algorithms in PIACERE

The task T5.3, named as *Best configuration deployments based on optimization algorithms*, is dedicated to the development of an automatic optimization tool in charge of selecting and deploying the optimal Infrastructure as Code (IaC) configuration based on a set of constraints and requirements. To reach this objective, beside the Optimizer, the IOP also includes an infrastructural elements catalogue where the relevant characteristics and features of all available elements are described.

On the one hand, the IEC is a persistence component which has the main function of storing all the information needed by different PIACERE components. For any persistence component, two critical aspects should be covered on the implementation of the IEC: how the information is 1) added and 2) retrieved. Related to the information feed, three main interactions exist among the IEC and other PIACERE components: 1) the GUI/IDE based on Eclipse, 2) the PIACERE Runtime Controller (PRC), and 3) the monitoring components. Regarding the usage of the information stored in the IEC, just the interaction with the Optimizer, part of the IOP, should be considered.

On the other hand, the optimization problem modelled for covering the necessities established in the PIACERE project consists of having a service to be deployed, and the objective of finding an optimized deployment configuration of the IaC on the appropriate infrastructural elements that best fulfil the predefined restrictions and constraints. It is the IOP Optimizer which, in this context, has the responsibility of finding these optimized deployment configurations given the input data received. This input data is provided in DOML format, and it include the optimization objectives and the optimization requirements. After receiving this information, the IOP Optimizer conducts the matchmaking for the infrastructure via the execution of a multi/many-objective optimization method against the information available in the IEC.

Lastly, two additional aspects should be deemed within the IOP Optimizer:

- The first aspect is that the problem to be solved could be composed of several conflicting objectives (such as costs and performance of the provisioned infrastructure resources). This situation requires the implementation of a multi- or even a many-objective optimization approach.
- The second issue is that two different optimizations are planned to be conducted in the context of PIACERE project: the initial deployment of the service, and the redeployment of an already running service (for instance, if the *Self-Healing* component decides that this is necessary).

3 Optimization in PIACERE

In this section, we contextualize the optimization problem that will be dealt in the frame of PIACERE project. To do that, first, we summarize in Section 3.1.1 the optimization modelled for M12 and described in previous version of this deliverable. This first version of the problem serves as a starting point for Section 3.1.2, in which we explain how the problem has evolved in last year up to M24. After that, in Section 3.13, we briefly describe how the optimization will be addressed on each of the use cases that will contemplate the adoption of the IOP.

3.1.1 Preliminarily Modeled Optimization Problem

As mentioned, the IOP is responsible for finding the best possible infrastructure given the input data received in DOML format. After receiving the corresponding information, the IOP Optimizer runs intelligent optimization algorithms considering the IEC in order to find the best matchmaking for the infrastructure. In other words, the Optimizer employs optimization algorithms for finding an optimized deployment configuration of the IaC on the appropriate infrastructural elements.

The IOP can be considered successful if the deployment configuration provided are good enough for meeting the users' requirements and needs. To this end, several deployment configurations will be shown and ranked using one of the objectives as ranking reference.

For adequately understanding the problem preliminarily defined in M12, we introduce here a brief example with a reduced IEC. Thus, we can consider a use case in which the user needs to deploy three different elements: [Virtual Machine, Database, Storage].

Additionally, five different elements can be found in this reduced IEC for each of these categories:

- Virtual Machine: [A3_France, A2_USA, B8_Germany, C1_Spain, c2_Europe]
- Database: [dynamo.4, m3.medium, mysql.AZ_1, postgresQL.G, r4.4xlarge]
- Storage: [Standard_Europe, Standard_USA, Storage3_Spain, G_1, AZ_3]

All these elements have associated some specific features such as the availability, cost, region, provider or cost.

Thus, the main objective is to find the best combination of [Virtual Machine, Database, Storage] which optimized some preliminarily defined objectives, such as the cost and performance. To find the best solutions for this reduced problem, the solving algorithm selected (which is the NSGA-II [1] for single and two-objective multi-objective problems and the NSGA-III [2] for three-objective multi-objective problems) defined each element of the IEC as an optimization variable using numerical values. For instance, the Virtual Machine element can adopt this group of values {0:"A3_France", 1:"A2_USA", 2:"B8_Germany", 3:"C1_Spain", 4:"C2_Europe"}. This way, the NSGA-II can obtain an example feasible solution with this form:

$$[0, 3, 1]: [295.5, 125.2]$$

This potential solution codifies a [Virtual Machine, Database, Storage] combination with the numerical value assignment. The array [0, 3, 1] represents [A3_France, postgresQL.G, Standard_USA]. Additionally, this solution has a cost and a performance associated, represented in the second array [295.5, 125.2], meaning that the cost of this solution is 295.5 while its performance is 125.2.

3.1.2 Evolving the Modeled Optimization Problem

In the second year of project, the optimization problem has been severely evolved in order to be prepared to be adapted to the needs of use case owners. In this subsection we will point out each of the new features associated with the optimization problem.

3.1.2.1 Adapting the IOP to the DOML format for acquiring optimization related input

The main novelty regarding the IOP, and also the optimization problem, is the adaptation to the DOML format. Thus, the optimization process through the IOP Optimizer will be conducted using a DOML file as input. More specifically, the DOML introduced as input to the IOP should contain a specific part coined as Optimization.

Having said that, in order to correctly run the Optimizer, the following structure should be added to the input DOML:

```

optimization opt {
    objectives {
    }
    nonfunctional_requirements {
    }
}

```

3.1.2.2 Choosing the optimization objectives through the input DOML

Using the structure defined in Section 3.1.2.1, the IOP permits the consideration of different kind and number of objectives. At this moment, three different objectives can be contemplated in the IOP: minimize the **cost**, maximize the **availability** and maximize the **performance**. These three tentative objectives have been selected after several meetings with use case owners and with the main intention of adapting the IOP to their needs.

Thus, any combination of these objectives can be introduced, which means that the IOP can contemplate a two-objective and three-objective multi-objective problem to solve. Here is an example of the full three objectives and how they should be introduced in the input DOML for considering a three-objective multi-objective problem.

```

objectives {
    "cost" => min
    "availability" => max
    "performance" => max
}

```

3.1.2.3 Introducing the non-functional requirements to the IOP

In addition to the optimization objectives, the IOP has been adapted also for contemplating the definition of a set of non-functional requirements for being considered in the optimization process. Again, these requirements have been established following the interest expressed by use case owners.

Thus, five different kinds of requirements are contemplated for the current version of the IOP:

- Assign a **maximum cost** for the overall configuration,
- Assign a **minimum availability** for the overall configuration,

- Assign a **minimum performance** for the overall configuration
- **Restrict the region** of the selected elements
- **Restrict the providers** of the elements.

With all this, here is an example of the five requirements, and how they should be introduced in the `nonfunctional_requirements` part depicted in previous Section 3.1.2.1:

```
nonfunctional_requirements {
    req1 "Cost <= 200.0" max 200.0 => "cost";
    req2 "Availability >= 98.0%" min 98.0 => "availability";
    req3 "Performance >= 10.0%" min 98.0 => "performance";
    req4 "Region" values "00EU" => "region";
    req5 "Provider" values "AMAZ" => "provider";
}
```

As can be seen, cost, availability and performance are introduced as double values, while region and provider features should be defined using `string`-based keys. These keys value should be compliant with the ones depicted and available in the IEC for each of the available element.

Finally, regarding the optimization process, the definition of this kind of requirements will determine the search space of the optimization algorithm. Once this solution space is defined, the algorithm is run guaranteeing that **all solutions provided as output compulsorily meet every one of the requirements** defined. In other words, **solutions that do not meet all requirements will be categorized as unfeasible** and will not be returned as result to the user.

3.1.2.4 *Considering the multi-element optimization*

The multi-element optimization is a feature added to the IOP after several meetings with the use case owners. Despite being considered as non-functional requirement, its impact in the optimization process is such that we have consider describing it in depth in this separated version, instead of describing it in Section 3.1.2.3.

As we have summarized in Section 3.1.1, the previous version of the optimization problem modelled in M12 consists of finding the best combination of each element that can be found in the IEC. That means that if the IEC has inside three kind of elements, such as `virtual machines`, `storages` and `databases`, so the Optimizer finds solutions that best combine 1 `virtual machine`, 1 `storage` and 1 `database`. In other words, each solution is comprised by one single unit of each available element.

This restrictive situation is not enough for attending the needs of use case owners, which can have the necessity of deploying more than one unit of each element. In response to this need, multi-element functionality has been implemented for the IOP.

In order to contemplate the new multi-element optimization, the user can introduce the following structure as a new requirement:

```
nonfunctional_requirements {
    req1 "elements" => "";
}
```

Using this structure, the user is able to introduce the combination of elements he/she is searching for. For example, if the user needs to deploy a service with 3 different `virtual machines` and 1 database (named as DB), the element part should be:

```
nonfunctional_requirements {
    req1 "elements" => "VM, VM, VM, DB";
}
```

That is, the elements requirement should be introduced as a list of Strings, being VM the acronym of Virtual Machine. In order to facilitate the usage of this multi-optimization feature, several aspects should be taken into account:

- The IOP is flexible to the order of the `elements` part. That is, if the user needs to deploy 2 `virtual machines` and 2 `storages`, he/she can define the `elements` part without adapting to any established order. In other words, the following three examples represent the same situation above mentioned:

```
req1 "elements" => "VM, VM, storage, storage";
req1 "elements" => "storage, storage, VM, VM";
req1 "elements" => "VM, storage, VM, storage";
```

- The number of units per element can be equal to 0. In these cases, the `elements` parts should not contain the elements that are not desired. For example, if the user needs the best configuration for three different `virtual machines`, not needing any `storage` nor `database`, so the `elements` part should be defined as follows:

```
req1 "elements" => "VM, VM, VM";
```

- The `elements` part of the `nonfunctional_requirements` is optional. In case the user does not introduce this information, the IOP consider the basic problem. That is, the finding of the best configuration combining one single unit per element of the IEC.

3.1.2.5 How the IOP return the solutions

One of the most important aspects decided for the IOP is to determine how the solutions found by the Optimizer are returned to the user. At this point of the project, M24, it has been decided that the IOP returns a complete DOML. This DOML is an extension of the one introduced as input, with the optimization results introduced. First, the IOP complements the `optimization opt` part of the DOML adding the found solutions. This is an example:

```
optimization opt {
    objectives {
        "cost" => min
        "performance" => max
        "availability" => max
    }
    nonfunctional_requirements {
        req1 "Cost <= 400" max 400.0 => "cost";
    }
}
```

```

    req2 "Performance >= 60%" min 60.0 => "performance";
    req3 "Region" values "00EU" => "region";
    req4 "elements" => "VM, storage";
  }
  solution sol1 {
    objectives {
      cost 192.0 euro
      performance 65.83333333333333 metric
      availability 105.0 %
    }
    decisions ["[Storage1_Spain, VM_1_CS]"]
  }
  solution sol2 {
    objectives {
      cost 201.0 euro
      performance 65.93333333333334 metric
      availability 103.0 %
    }
    decisions ["[Storage4_Europe, VM_1_CS]"]
  }
}

```

In this example, the IOP returns two different solutions (`sol1` and `sol2`), which optimize the objectives introduced as input (cost, performance and availability), and which meet the three requirements introduced (`req1`, related with the cost; `req2`, related with the performance; and `req3`, related with the region). As can be seen in `req4`, the user searches for the best configurations composed by a single Virtual Machine and a single Storage element.

For each solution, the value of each objective is depicted in the section `objectives` of each solution, the elements chosen are listed in the `decisions` part.

Lastly, the IOP introduces the features of each found solution in the `concretizations` part of the DOML. This specific part of the DOML describes all elements that compose the solution, introducing all their features. If `concretizations` part is not present in the input DOML, the IOP creates it. For further information about the DOML and its different parts, we recommend the reading of deliverable D3.1 and D3.2. The following is an example of returning concretizations, considering a solution with just one virtual machine.

```

concrete_infrastructure con_infra {
  provider openstack {
    vm concrete_vm {
      properties {
        vm_name = "nginx-host";
        vm_key_name = "user1";
      }
    }
  }
}

```


For this reason, the IOP will show several deployment configurations, and these solutions will be ranked, in order to meet the success criteria shown in the DoA related to the **KR9 – IaC Optimized Platform (IOP)**:

Success criteria: The IOP is able to propose the most optimized deployment configuration of the infrastructural code taking into consideration the constraints predefined. To this end, several deployment configurations will be shown and ranked.

For this reason, the IOP provides the different deployment configurations found using one of the optimization objectives as reference. In this sense, and in order to do it flexible enough, the IOP adapts to the needs of the user, who can define which is the objective considered as reference. For doing that, the input DOML is used. More concretely, the `objectives` part of the `optimization_opt` section of the DOML is used, deeming the first value as reference objective.

Thus, if the user inserts the following objectives as input:

```
objectives {
    "cost" => min
    "availability" => max
    "performance" => max
}
```

All the deployments returned by the IOP will be ranked using the cost as reference, choosing the solution with the less cost the first one to appear. On the contrary, if the user introduces the following objectives:

```
objectives {
    "performance" => max
    "availability" => max
}
```

The performance will be the reference to rank the returned solutions, choosing these solutions with the best performance as the best ones.

3.1.3 Optimization relevance to the use-cases

In this brief section, we describe the role that the IOP plays in each of the use cases contemplated in PIACERE. Thus, in Section 3.1.3.2 we detail the relevance of the IOP in SI-MPA's use case, while Section 3.1.3.2 is devoted to detail the importance of the tool in the Prodevelop's scenario.

3.1.3.1 The IOP in the SI-MPA use case

In SI-MPA use case (UC1, more information in deliverables D7.1 and D7.2) we see benefit of the implementation of an automatic optimization tool (IOP) in charge of selecting and deploying the optimal IaC infrastructural and resource configuration based on a set of constraints (the optimization of RAM, CPU, and disk, cost of resources which reflect in the license price) will be able to run in a dynamic-definition environment (with elements which are dynamically updated depending on their performance). Expectation is that the IOP is able to propose the most optimized deployment configuration of the infrastructural code taking into consideration the constraints predefined.

3.1.3.2 The IOP in the Prodevelop use case

The integration of PIACERE's IOP capabilities with Posidonia (UC2, more information in deliverables D7.1 and D7.2) will increase its competitive advantage, providing an approach which is capable of being adapted to customer needs. Thus, a double improvement is expected. On the one hand, the solution will be more easily adaptable to other web service providers such as Google Cloud, Azure, AWS, etc. On the other hand, the restrictions proposed by customers in terms of availability, cost, supplier, etc. requirements can be easily satisfied.

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4 Catalogue Implementation

4.1 Changes in v2

With respect to the first implementation of the Catalogue, which was described in the previous version of this deliverable (D5.7 [3]), the functionality offered by the second version is fundamentally the same. Minor changes have been done in the Catalogue, just to make possible and polish the integration with the IOP, the PRC and the IDE. Internal changes with regard to the simplification of the compilation and deployment in local and integration environments have also been performed during this time.

The new version of the Catalogue is, therefore, integrated via API with these three aforementioned components. Also, the content of the Catalogue has been updated with the inclusion of some of the services that OpenStack offers in its basic flavours. In this sense, we can state that main work of the period has been dedicated to the integration tasks of the Catalogue with the rest of components.

Accordingly, the sections of Technical description, Package information and Installation instructions remain mainly unchanged. In the Functional description, all around requirement's status and sequence diagram have been modified, trying to clarify how the interaction happens, and what is the workflow of actions in which the catalogue is involved. The User Manual is totally revamped showing the handling of the Catalogue both as integrated in the PIACERE IDE and as a separate tool. Changes also apply to Licensing information and Download sections.

Other changes in the Catalogue, that are still work-in-progress tasks, have to do with the suggestions made by the experts during the first review. First, they refer to the way the Catalogue was updated: a manual process performed by an administrator. Second, they refer to the alignment of the PIACERE Catalogue and the Gaia-X specifications. We will briefly explain the approach about these two items in the following sub-sections.

4.1.1 Automatic updating

Regarding the possible automation of the Catalogue data, a preliminary analysis has been done in order to implement a proof-of-concept of this type of functionality. At this respect, an open-source library has been identified that is able to provide this feature. This software library is part of the developments of the MELODIC EU project¹, and it is intended to get the information of public cloud services in an automated manner.

The path in the following year is to leverage this software piece integrating it in the Catalogue in order to provide some automatic updating mechanism.

4.1.2 Gaia-X Federation Services

In the previous version of this deliverable (D5.7 [3]), a reduced state-of-the-art about the Gaia-X architecture model was introduced. More concretely, the conceptual model, the Federation Services concept and the self-description idea were described. In the *Appendix C. IEC Scenarios*

The scenarios of IEC are described in this appendix.

FEATURE: PIACERE Design Time

¹ <https://h2020.melodic.cloud/consortium/>

Scenario: IOP working

Given the IOP need the Catalogue data to calculate optimizations

When the IOP invokes the IEC

Then the IEC returns the available elements in json format

FEATURE: PIACERE Run Time

Scenario: A project is being deployed

Given the deployment is successful

Then the PRC sends to the IEC the info about the deployed elements

And the IEC stores the information, including which service is deployed (type, id...)

And the IEC (periodically) connects to monitoring

And gets information about the deployed services

Scenario: A project is being undeployed

Given the un-deployment is successful

Then the PRC sends to the IEC the info about the deployed elements

And the IEC stores the information, including which service is undeployed (type, id...)

DRAFT

Appendix D. About Gaia-X, we include an updated version of it.

To illustrate the discussion, we introduce some concepts here. The Gaia-X conceptual model is shown in Figure 1. The Gaia-X core concepts are represented in classes. The upper part of the model shows different actors of Gaia-X (highlighted in blue), while the lower part shows elements of commercial trade and the relationship to actors outside Gaia-X.

Figure 1: Gaia-X Conceptual model. Source: Gaia-X European Association for Data and Cloud AISBL [4]

- A *Provider* is a *Participant* who operates *Resources* in the Gaia-X Ecosystem. The *Provider* defines the *Service Offering* including terms and conditions as well as technical Policies. Furthermore, it provides the *Service Instance* that includes a *Self-Description* and associated Policies.
- A *Consumer* is a *Participant* who searches *Service Offerings* and consumes *Service Instances* in the Gaia-X Ecosystem to enable digital offerings for *End-Users*.

- A *Service Offering* is defined as a set of *Resources*, which a *Provider* aggregates and publishes as a single entry in a *Catalogue*. *Service Offerings* may themselves be aggregated realizing *Service Composition*.
- A *Service Instance* is the instantiation of a *Service Offering* at runtime, strictly bound to a version of a *Self-Description*.

Regarding the Gaia-X conceptual model, the PIACERE Catalogue would be a Service Instance, offered by a Provider which would be Tecnalía (due to the specifications of the Gaia-X Trust Framework², a Participant must adhere to certain verification mechanisms cryptographic signatures validation).

The path to follow in next year is to define the PIACERE Catalogue as a Service Offering of Tecnalía, and to register it in the Gaia-X catalogue of services. This has to be done using the Gaia-X SD or Self-Descriptions³ (a SD describe Entities from the Gaia-X Conceptual Model in a machine interpretable format). This includes Self-Descriptions for the Participants themselves, as well as the Resources and Service Offerings from the Providers. We can divide this process into several steps to be followed:

1. Create the certificate of Tecnalía as a Participant. This will be used to sign SDs.
2. Create the SD for the Participant Tecnalía, and validate it with the Gaia-X service
3. Create the SD for the PIACERE Catalogue and validate it.
4. Register the Catalogue in Gaia-X Catalogue

The steps 1 and 2 are already accomplished. The self-description of Participant Tecnalía⁴ can be seen in the next listing, in the JSON.SD format. It has already been validated by Gaia-X services. The other steps will be tackled in the Y3 of the project.

```
{
-  selfDescriptionCredential: {
-    @context: [
      - "https://www.w3.org/2018/credentials/v1",
      - "https://registry.gaia-x.eu/v2206/api/shape"
    ],
-    type: [
      - "VerifiableCredential",
      - "LegalPerson"
    ],
-    id: "https://hodeix.digital.tecnalia.dev/.well-known/participantTecnalia.json",
-    issuer: "did:web:hodeix.digital.tecnalia.dev",
-    issuanceDate: "2022-09-27T09:36:23.235Z",
-    credentialSubject: {
      - id: "did:web:hodeix.digital.tecnalia.dev",
      - gx-participant:legalName: "Fundacion Tecnalía Research & Innovation",
      - gx-participant:website: "https://www.tecnalia.com/",
      - gx-participant:registrationNumber: {
        gx-participant:registrationNumberType: "vatID",
        gx-participant:registrationNumberNumber: "ESG48975767"
      },
      - gx-participant:headquarterAddress: {
```

² <https://gaia-x.gitlab.io/policy-rules-committee/trust-framework/>

³ <https://docs.gaia-x.eu/technical-committee/architecture-document/22.04/self-description/>

⁴ <https://hodeix.digital.tecnalia.dev/.well-known/participantTecnalia.json>

```

      gx-participant:addressCountryCode: "ES",
      gx-participant:addressCode: "ES-PV",
      gx-participant:street-address: "Parque Cientifico y
      Tecnologico de Bizkaia, Edificio 700",
      gx-participant:postal-code: "48160",
      gx-participant:locality: "Derio"
    },
  - gx-participant:legalAddress: {
    gx-participant:addressCountryCode: "ES",
    gx-participant:addressCode: "ES-PV",
    gx-participant:street-address: "Parque Cientifico y
    Tecnologico de Gipuzkoa, Mikeletegi Pasalekua 2",
    gx-participant:postal-code: "20009",
    gx-participant:locality: "San Sebastian"
  },
  - gx-participant:termsAndConditions:
    "70c1d713215f95191a11d38fe2341faed27d19e083917bc8732ca4fea4976
    700"
  },
- proof: {
  type: "JsonWebSignature2020",
  created: "2022-10-18T06:51:48.649Z",
  proofPurpose: "assertionMethod",
  verificationMethod: "did:web:hodeix.digital.tecnalia.dev",
  jws:
  "eyJhbGciOiJIUzI1NiIsImI2NCI6ZmFsc2UsImNyaXQiOlsiYjY0Ii119..kbjXzBz
  vSE7fPDKHoPIs0ScenJc7nYAR9tk6_..."
},
- complianceCredential: {
  @context: [
    "https://www.w3.org/2018/credentials/v1"
  ],
  type: [
    "VerifiableCredential",
    "ParticipantCredential"
  ],
  id: "https://catalogue.gaia-
  x.eu/credentials/ParticipantCredential/1666075916527",
  issuer: "did:web:compliance.gaia-x.eu",
  issuanceDate: "2022-10-18T06:51:56.527Z",
  credentialSubject: {
    id: "did:web:hodeix.digital.tecnalia.dev",
    hash:
    "cd4671eb4fa46e9ae80284dae339e6171f7738d481e1bc72db88bfa632452917"
  },
  proof: {
    type: "JsonWebSignature2020",
    created: "2022-10-18T06:51:56.527Z",
    proofPurpose: "assertionMethod",
    jws:
    "eyJhbGciOiJIUzI1NiIsImI2NCI6ZmFsc2UsImNyaXQiOlsiYjY0Ii119..qDGT7bU
    1W9tG3hl9VpsxCIV67HeCNsc_nd3lYleseQ...",
    verificationMethod: "did:web:compliance.gaia-x.eu"
  }
}

```

4.2 Functional description

The purpose of the catalogue is to manage the different infrastructure elements, using a data model that allows their classification based on properties. These characteristics, associated with

the services registered in the catalogue, allow an optimal deployment configuration by the optimization algorithms.

The catalogue will also provide status information for the deployed instances and receive information about tore down instances.

The user's requirements satisfied by this version are described in Table 1. They are aligned with D2.2 deliverable [2], which details the whole list of PIACERE requirements.

Table 1: Requirements covered

Req ID	Description	Status	Requirement Coverage at M24
REQ3	IOP will include a catalogue of infrastructural elements (e.g. (edge, node) computation, networks, cloud services (e.g. IaaS, PaaS, SaaS) classifiable by a set of constraints (e.g. memory, disk, ...). This catalogue of infrastructural elements should be clearly defined, including possible restrictions and dynamic variations. These infrastructural elements will be transformed as optimization variables, and they will be intelligently treated by the optimization algorithm seeking to find the best configuration deployment.	Satisfied	The REQ3 requirement has been satisfied, being the Catalogue already defined, implemented and the connection with the IOP tested.
REQ4	Provide the means for the IOP to properly consume all the data related to the catalogue of infrastructural elements status, as well as their characteristics and possible variations. Special mention shall be done here to the values monitored by the self-learning algorithm / monitoring component. This module shall provide real measures regarding the infrastructural elements in order to update their characteristics.	Partially satisfied	The REQ4 is partially satisfied. The IOP already consumes the data of the Catalogue to find the optimized deployment configuration. There are work in process parts that have to do with the dynamic information related to the services deployed and being monitored. This information is being stored in the monitoring database and can be shown to the user in ad-hoc dashboards, but the connection with the Catalogue has still to be implemented.

4.2.1 Fitting into overall PIACERE Architecture

The Infrastructural Elements Catalogue (IEC) is one of the components of the PIACERE architecture. Although, in some sense, it is considered part of the IOP (IOP is the key result KR9, which includes the IEC), in this section we detach them, to better understand its interactions.

The Catalogue interacts with these tools in the PIACERE ecosystem, as can be seen in the following Sequence Diagram (Figure 2):

- The GUI/IDE, that endorses or includes element information in the Catalogue.
- The IOP, to whom it provides information about available elements and its related dynamic information.
- The Runtime Controller (PRC), from which receives information (that is originated in the IEM) about deployed instances or tore down instances.
- The Runtime Monitoring, that provides monitoring information of the running instances.

Figure 2: Sequence Diagram of the Infrastructural Elements Catalogue

4.3 Technical description

This subsection describes the technical specification of this second prototype. First, the main architecture of the prototype is shown and described, along with the description of all components. This subsection finishes with the technical specifications of the developed system.

4.3.1 Architecture and component's description

IEC architecture is based on a microservices style, hence it is divided in a front-end and a backend, so that's it's easier to scale and survive infrastructure issues. The main purposes of these components are described in the following.

Figure 3: Main architecture of the Infrastructural Elements Catalogue

The IEC is composed by two principal components, which main purposes are briefly described as follows (for further details, see the section 6.1 *Package Information*).

- **IEC-Frontend:** this component is the entry point of the IEC system. All the external callings to the whole IEC are made through it. There are two main uses of this component, the frontend for managing the service Catalogue and the API exposed services to interact with other components.
- **IEC-Backend:** this component cannot be accessed externally. It manages all the logic of the IEC and exposes the rest API services to the other components.

4.3.2 Technical specifications

The technical specification of the prototype can be summarized in the following points:

- This prototype has been developed using **JHipster Framework** [5]. The framework provides all the needed for a modern web application and microservice architecture.
- It uses **Spring boot** for application configuration.
- In the client side, IEC-Frontend gateway uses **Yeoman, Webpack, Angular** and **Bootstrap** technologies.
- In the server side, IEC-Backend microservice, uses Maven, Spring, Spring MVC Rest, Spring Data JPA and Netflix OSS.
- For access control the JSON Web Token (**JWT**) mechanism is used. This is a stateless security mechanism which uses a secure token holding the user's login name and authorities.
- Data persistence is implemented in a **MySQL** database.

- The **JHipster Registry** offers service discovery using Netflix Eureka.

5 IOP Optimizer Implementation

5.1 Changes in v2

As mentioned previously, the optimization problem modelled for PIACERE and solved by the IOP consists of a service to be deployed and the IEC, with the main objective of finding an optimized deployment configuration of the IaC on the appropriate infrastructural elements that best meet the predefined constraints. For solving this problem, the IOP should seek for the most optimized deployment configurations considering the main requirements and needs of the user. Also, because of the nature of the problem, more than one optimum solution can exist. For this reason, the IOP Optimizer should provide several configurations to the user, ranked as described in Section 3.1.2.6.

With all this, this first implementation of the Optimizer, described in the previous version of this deliverable (D5.7) consists of a laboratory prototype working with a reduced, controlled, and static IEC. That first prototype includes a wide variety of multi-objective algorithms, and two different optimization formulations (continuous and discrete). Additionally, two different well-known optimization frameworks were considered: jMetal [6] and MOEA [7].

This first prototype has been evolved in order to develop a use-case oriented IOP Optimizer, which is the tool described in this section, and the outcome of the work done until M24 of the project. The newly generated Optimizer is now DOML compliant, being able to gather all the information that the user introduces to the system. The IOP extracts this information and conducts an adapted optimization, considering the optimization objectives and all the optimization requirements introduced by the user. To develop this version of the tool, the jMetal framework has been chosen as the basis. Furthermore, the NSGA-II has been contemplated for single and two-objective multi-objective problems, and the NSGA-III for three-objective multi-objective problems.

It should be pointed here that both NSGA-II and NSGA-III have been chosen as solving algorithms because of their contrasted well-performance [8]. Furthermore, NSGA-III has been considered for many-objective instances of the problem, because it was conceived for solving this kind of situations (despite some bibliographic do not completely support this theory [9]). In any case, the selection of these algorithms is preliminary, and the final decision on what algorithms will be part of the final version of the IOP is still pending. This decision will be made based on a comprehensive experimentation using different multi-objective and may-objective methods, and it will be reported in the next version of this deliverable (D5.9).

The main innovation of this second version of the IOP Optimizer is the adaptation of the optimization problem to the use-case oriented requirements, providing a flexible tool which can easily embrace the needs of the end users. Furthermore, the integration with the IEC and DOML language has been already done, and the methods for ranking the provided solutions have been performed.

Regarding the content depicted on this deliverable and related with the IOP Optimizer, despite sections such as 5.2, 7.1 and 3.1.1 reuse some little pieces of text previously shown in deliverable D5.7, most of the content used in this manuscript is completely new.

As a conclusion, a more realistic IOP Optimizer is available for testing in the real-world use cases of the project.

5.2 Functional description

The user requirements satisfied by this interim version are described in Table 2. All these requirements have been obtained from the *PIACERE WP2 Requirements* internal document.

Table 2: user requirements satisfied by the optimizer.

Req ID	Description	Status	Requirement Coverage at M24
REQ03	IOP will include a catalogue of infrastructural elements (e.g. (edge, node) computation, networks, cloud services (e.g. IaaS, PaaS, SaaS)) classifiable by a set of constraints (e.g. memory, disk, ...). This catalogue of infrastructural elements should be clearly defined, including possible restrictions and dynamic variations. These infrastructural elements will be transformed as optimization variables, and they will be intelligently treated by the optimization algorithm seeking to find the best configuration deployment.	Partially satisfied	The connection between the Optimizer and the IEC is already made, and it works properly. The optimization is performed using the elements that compose the IEC. As next step, the IEC should be fed with additional and more heterogeneous elements and should introduce dynamism on its elements.
REQ04	Provide the means for the IOP to properly consume all the data related with the catalogue of infrastructural elements status, as well as their characteristics and possible variations. Special mention shall be done here to the values monitored by the self-learning algorithm / monitoring component. This module shall provide real measures regarding the infrastructural elements in order to update their characteristics.	Partially satisfied	The Optimizer properly consumes the data of the IEC, and it properly takes all its characteristics for conducting the optimization. Next steps include the consideration of the measures coming from self-learning and self-healing for updating the characteristics of the IEC elements.
REQ12	The IEM shall allow redeployment and reconfiguration, both full and partial, as allowed by the used IaC technology.	Discarded	This requirement was finally discarded, since it corresponds to other KR.
REQ37	CSE to have a simulated mode limited to provisioning.	Discarded	This requirement was finally discarded, since it corresponds to other KR.
REQ46	The monitoring component shall gather metrics from the instances of the infrastructural elements at run time. These metrics need to be related to the NFR and accessible to the IOP (through the dynamic part of the infrastructural catalogue)	To start	The IOP will be able to access the information modified by the monitoring component, since these modifications will be directly done on the IEC. In any case, this connection between the IEC and the monitoring

			system has not been done yet.
REQ98	The IOP components provide feedback on the DOML code, without doing automatic writes. The end user can choose to accept or not the feedback received. (ex REQ56&75)	Satisfied	The Optimizer receives a DOML as input, and it provides as solution the same DOML but with the results of the optimization inserted.

Furthermore, the internal requirements satisfied up to M24 are described in Table 3. These requirements are the continuation of those depicted in the previous version of this deliverable, and they have been polished and adapted as the project advances.

Table 3: internal requirements satisfied by the optimizer

Req ID	Description	Status	Requirement Coverage at M24
WP5.3-REQ1	Load/read information about the catalogue of infrastructural elements	Satisfied	The connection between the IEC and the Optimizer has been satisfactorily carried out.
WP5.3-REQ2	IOP shall consider both functional and non-functional requirements for searching the best solutions that fit the user demand.	Satisfied	This requirement was already satisfied in M12. In any case, in this new stage of the project, the consideration of this requirements is done through DOML language. Furthermore, in this second year of the project additional requirements have been considered and implemented (such as the multi-element optimization or the choosing of a provider).
WP5.3-REQ3	IOP shall use optimization algorithms such as genetic algorithms and provide a set of potential combinations of elements that fulfill the established user requirements.	Satisfied	This requirement has also been satisfied in M12. In any case, up to M24 further advances have been conducted on this aspect. These advances contemplate the adaptation of the algorithms to the use-case oriented problem and the ranking of the provided solutions.
WP5.3-REQ4	The IOP should be able to obtain the information provided by the user in DOML language	Satisfied	The IOP understands DOML language and can obtain the information related to the optimization objectives and requirements properly.

5.2.1 Fitting into overall PIACERE Architecture

Regarding the fitting of the IOP Optimizer in the PIACERE overall architecture, an interesting modification has been conducted with respect to the first version of this deliverable (D5.7). As mentioned in our previous deliverable, the IOP is one of the tools of PIACERE, and it is placed in the phase of PIACERE Run Time (Figure 4). In any case, after this second year of project, it has been revealed that the IOP should also be placed in the PIACERE Design Time phase (Figure 5).

The IOP receives all the information about the available elements from the IEC. These elements are transformed in optimization variables and are employed for optimizing the functional and non-functional requirements. Obtained optimized solutions are provided to the Runtime Controller when the service is called if the self-learning has detected the necessity of finding a new deployment configuration. Furthermore, the IOP can also be called in the Design Time phase, when the first deployment is needed. In this situation, the user can ask for the optimization of the deployment through the PIACERE IDE.

Having said that, the role of the IOP in both Run Time and Design Phase can be summarized as follows:

- *Role of the IOP in the Run Time phase:* in this phase, the IOP is involved in the self-healing process when needed asking for a re-deployment, and it is called by the PIACER Runtime Controller.
- *Role of the IOP in the Design Time Phase:* in this case, the IDE can call the IOP as an optional step (user choice), after the DOML Model Checker interaction. Thus, the IOP will return the optimization to the IDE, and the user can accept or not the proposed optimization.

Figure 4: PIACERE Run Time Diagram on its 2.0 version

Figure 5: PIACERE Design Time Diagram on its 2.0 version

Further information about the modifications conducted on the architecture of the whole PIACERE ecosystem and the placement of the whole IOP will be available in the upcoming Deliverable D2.2, released in M23.

5.3 Technical description

This subsection is devoted to describing the technical specification of this second version of the IOP Optimizer. First, the main composition of the component is shown and described in Section 5.3.1. *Architecture and component's description*. After that, the technical specifications of the developed system are described in Section 5.3.2. *Technical Specifications* This subsection finishes with Section 5.3.3, in which we justify the utilization of jMetal as base framework

5.3.1 Architecture and component's description

Despite the objective and the operation of the evolved version of the IOP follows the same philosophy as the first prototype, the structure of the tool has been substantially modified, in order to implement a more use-case oriented and realistic system. We depict in Figure 6 the current composition of the tool.

Figure 6: Composition of the IOP Optimizer

Thus, the main components of the Optimizer can be summarized as follows. It should be noted that further detail of this components is provided in the upcoming Section 7.1 *Package information*.

- **Optimizer Service:** the optimizer service is the entry point of the system, and the class that is called by external components. In a nutshell, the optimizer service gathers the input data (provided in DOML language), builds the optimization problem, and initialize both the solving algorithm algorithms and the data reader procedure. Classes devoted to this duty are placed in the newly created `com.piacere.iop.optimizer.service`.
- **Data Reader:** this component has the main objective of gathering the data from the IEC and process them for being used as optimization variables by the solver. This component conducts some data-processing procedures such as data cleaning, normalization, discretization or integration. Classes devoted to this duty are placed in the newly created `com.piacere.iop.optimizer.service`.
- **Solving algorithms:** This is the component in which the solving algorithms are comprised. In the evolved version of the Optimizer, these solvers have been developed using jMetal framework. In overall, 21 different algorithms are available. Despite NSGA-II and NSGA-III methods have been chosen for being the solving techniques used in the IOP, the rest of the algorithms have been maintained for further testing purposes. On this regard, it is important to highlight here that, at this stage of development, the IOP is a multi-method platform, which resorts to the NSGA-II for solving single and two-objective multi-objective problems, and NSGA-III for three-objective multi-objective problems. Moreover, as in the previous version of the prototype, two different types of algorithms are available, which are characterized by the kind of variables they use: continuous and discrete. The main justification for maintaining these two algorithm types is also for further testing purposes. Classes devoted to this duty are placed in the newly created `com.piacere.iop.optimizer.algorithm.jmetal.continuous` and `com.piacere.iop.optimizer.algorithm.jmetal.discrete`.

- **Optimization problem building:** This component is dedicated to build the optimization problem for being subsequently solved by the artificial intelligence algorithms. It should be considered that in this version of the tool, the user preferences demand to the IOP the flexibility of generating optimization problems of different nature (single-objective, multi-objective, considering multi-element optimization...). Classes devoted to this duty are placed in the newly created `com.piacere.iop.optimizer.problem`.
- **Solution Processing Mechanism:** the purpose of this component is to obtain the outcomes reached by the solving algorithm and return them to the user in an understandable and ranked form. This component is also in charge of traducing the solutions to DOML format. Classes devoted to this duty are placed in the newly created `com.piacere.iop.optimizer.util`.
- **Web Service Component:** the last component has been newly created for this evolved version of the IOP, and it is charge of preparing the whole tool for being accessible by external components and tools of the PIACERE project. Classes devoted to this duty are placed in `com.piacere.iop.optimizer`, `com.piacere.iop.optimizer.aop.logging`, `com.piacere.iop.optimizer.client`, `com.piacere.iop.optimizer.config`, `com.piacere.iop.optimizer.domain`, `com.piacere.iop.optimizer.repository`, `com.piacere.iop.optimizer.security`, `com.piacere.iop.optimizer.security.jwt`, `com.piacere.iop.optimizer.web.rest`, `com.piacere.iop.optimizer.web.rest.errors` and `com.piacere.iop.optimizer.web.rest.vm`.

5.3.2 Technical specifications

The second version of the IOP Optimizer has also been developed using JAVA, which is a high-level, general-purpose, class-based and object-oriented programming language. JAVA was conceived for having few dependencies, in order to be more efficient than other similar languages. Also, JAVA embraces the philosophy known as WORA, which is *Write Once and Run Anywhere*. This philosophy implies that the compiled JAVA code can be run in all platforms that support JAVA without requiring any additional recompilation.

Additionally, jMetal framework, crucial for the optimization algorithms, is imported using MAVEN mechanism, which is a software project management and comprehension tool. In the previous version of this tool MOEA framework was also imported using this mechanism, but as mentioned before, in this second version this framework is not used. MAVEN is based on a concept named as Project Object Model (POM). Thus, MAVEN can manage a build, reporting and documentation in a project from a unique file of information. Lastly, the latest version of jMetal 5.1 has been used, and for JAVA the 11 JDK.

Additionally, following the service-oriented architecture (SOA) approach that is shared among the different pieces of the PIACERE Framework, the logic of the IOP has been packaged as a service using Jhipster Framework. The Jhipster Framework is a free and open-source application generator used to develop web applications and Microservices using Angular and the Spring Framework. Jhipster has many goodness, that drove us to its usage. Some of the key ones were:

- The implementation of REST APIs
- The support of the Open API Specification (OAS)
- The inclusion of different security mechanism
- The horizontal scale capabilities

The Open API specification was quite important as it provides a standard way to describe the REST API. This issue allows us to quickly generate clients in different languages that facilitates the integration of other components inside and outside the PIACERE framework.

Finally, like other components in the PIACERE framework, the component is packaged using the docker technology and its integration in the piacere framework has been specified using the docker-compose choreography mechanisms.

It is worth mentioning that the Docker file used for the containerization of the IOP follows a multistage approach that covers both the compilation and packaging of the source code in a *jar*, and the running of that jar to provide the expected service. This is very beneficial to ensure the homogeneity of the behavior of the service provided by the resulting image.

5.3.3 Justification of using jMetal as base optimization framework

As properly described in previous D5.7, the first prototype of the IOP Optimizer supports the use of two different optimization frameworks: jMetal⁵ and MOEA⁶. These frameworks were selected for several reasons. On the one hand, jMetal is one of the most used optimization frameworks for solving multi-objective optimization problems. Furthermore, it also supports efficiently the dealing of single-objective and many-objective problems. jMetal is open-source, and it has a significant community which supports it, and which frequently develops new functionalities. Additionally, this framework allows the adoption of several optimization types, such as continuous and discrete (the ones studied in PIACERE), and it has been extensively employed by the optimization community for solving both academic and real-world problems.

On the other hand, MOEA is another well-known framework for dealing with optimization problems of different kind. As stated in the MOEA webpage, “*MOEA is a free and open-source Java library for developing and experimenting with multi-objective evolutionary algorithms and other general-purpose single and multi-objective optimization algorithms*”. MOEA has several advantages, such as its open-source nature, making easy not only the adaptation of the algorithms to the PIACERE problem, but also their extension to add custom mechanisms and functionalities. Furthermore, like jMetal, this platform has also a large community using it, and it counts with a valuable documentation.

In addition to MOEA and jMetal, additional frameworks were valued, but finally discarded. These platforms are JCLEC-MO⁷, Jenetic⁸ and ECJ⁹. We suggest any interested reader to analyse D5.7 to find the reasons for discarding these alternatives.

In the evolved version of the IOP, and with the intention of having a more use-case oriented system, the Optimizer should only employ a single algorithm, in order to give an answer to the user needs and provide the most optimized configurations. For this reason, one important decision taken in this second year of the project has been to finally decide which is the optimization framework used in the upcoming versions of the Optimizer. On this regard, the platform selected is jMetal, which is the one that is going to be used in the PIACERE IOP tool.

⁵ jmetal.github.io/JMetal/

⁶ moeaframework.org

⁷ <https://cs.gmu.edu/~eclab/projects/ecj/>

⁸ <https://www.uco.es/kdis/research/software/jclec-mo/>

⁹ <https://jenetics.io/>

It is important to note that both platforms are really valuable, and both could have been used for this purpose. In any case, there are several reasons that have led us to choose jMetal over MOEA:

- jMetal works better with single-objective problems.
- jMetal offers more algorithms for working with many-objective problems.
- Algorithms are more flexible to configure and modify in jMetal.
- The definition of the PIACERE problem has been demonstrated to be easier to conduct in jMetal in comparison to MOEA.

5.4 Connection among IOP Optimizer and the Catalogue of Infrastructural Elements

The connection between the IOP Optimizer (IOP) and the Catalogue of Infrastructural Elements (IEC) is critical in the sense that the IEC provides the IOP with the list of infrastructural elements that can be applied to the DOML in order to achieve the requested objectives.

Technically, the connection between the IOP and the IEC is implemented through the usage of the IEC REST API by the IOP. The IEC REST API is described using the OAS, that standard specification was used during the development of the client part at the IOP.

Using OAS bring many advantages during the development of the code in the IOP side that was responsible to invoke the IEC.

- It facilitates the manual test of the IEC in REST tools such as Postman (<https://www.postman.com/>) that helps the understanding of the behaviour of the different methods in the IEC specification, specially the one to be used by the IOP.
- It allows the automatic generation of clients using different generators such as swagger codegen (<https://swagger.io/tools/swagger-codegen/>) or OpenAPI generator <https://github.com/OpenAPITools/openapi-generator>. In the same way other assets can be generated such as testing elements, documentation, etc.

Specifically, the integration is based on the Stateless REST GET `/api/root-services/catalogue` method depicted below in Figure 7. This method returns a list of infrastructure resources that satisfies the criteria provided during the request of the method. Examples of criteria that IOP can apply based on the DOML information is the type or the location. If no criteria are provided the entire list of infrastructure resources is provided.

Name	Description
serviceClassId.equals integer(\$int64) (query)	serviceClassId.equals
serviceClassId.greaterThan integer(\$int64) (query)	serviceClassId.greaterThan
serviceClassId.greaterThanOrEqualTo integer(\$int64) (query)	serviceClassId.greaterThanOrEqualTo
serviceClassId.in array[integer] (query)	Add integer item
serviceClassId.lessThan integer(\$int64) (query)	serviceClassId.lessThan
serviceClassId.lessThanOrEqualTo integer(\$int64) (query)	serviceClassId.lessThanOrEqualTo
serviceClassId.notEquals integer(\$int64) (query)	serviceClassId.notEquals
serviceClassId.notIn array[integer]	Add integer item

Figure 7: root-services catalogue method

5.5 Future steps regarding IOP Optimizer

As can be read on the DoA of the project, task T5.3 ends at month 30. For this reason, several future steps have been planned around the IOP to be carried out until the end of the project. First of all, additional tests will be conducted with the use cases that compose the project. For sure, from these tests, the necessity of implementing several modifications and adjustments will arise. This work will be performed in the following months.

Additionally, an extensive *research-oriented* experimentation will be conducted with the Optimizer, with the main objective of clearly defining which are the most appropriate optimization algorithms to deem in the final version of the tool. For properly carrying out this experimentation, a significant benchmark of DOML instances and algorithms will be tested. This way, a set of 10 DOML test-examples of different nature will be build, considering diverse number of objectives and requirements.

With this benchmark generated, a group composed of an approximate amount of 10 multi-objective and many-objective algorithms will be test on all these instances, with the goal of determining which is the best one for being included in the final IOP Optimizer. Among the algorithms, alternatives such as NSGA-II, NSGA-III, SMPSO, MoCell, SPEA2 or MOMBI will be contemplated.

For properly extracting significant conclusions, each algorithm will be run several times on each instance, and a couple of statistical tests will be conducted for obtaining fair and rigorous conclusions. Tentatively, the statistical tests conducted will be the non-parametric Friedman Test and the post-hoc Holm' test.

Additionally, some further tests will be conducted with single-objective optimization, in order to conclude if the application of multi-objective and many-objective metaheuristic algorithms provide any advantage in comparison to classical single-objective optimization approaches.

As explained, this experimentation will be carried out in the following months, and it will be reported in the upcoming D5.9, delivered in M30.

6 Catalogue Delivery and usage

6.1 Package information

6.1.1 IEC-Backend

The main structure of the prototype developed in this first stage of the project is composed by the packages shown in the following Figure 8.

Figure 8: Structure of the catalogue

Each of these packages has its main objective and its context within the whole prototype. Furthermore, these packages are also comprised by several JAVA classes. With all this, the main purpose and composition of each component is as follows:

- `com.piacere.iec.backend.aop.logging`: this package is composed of `LoggingAspect.java` which define the aspect for logging execution of service and repository Spring components.
- `com.piacere.iec.backend.aop.client`: Composed by `UserFeignClientInterceptor.java` which implements `RequestInterceptor.java`. This class checks and add JWT token to the request header.
- `com.piacere.iec.backend.aop.config`: this package contains all classes related to configuration purposes.

Figure 9: structure of config package

- `com.piacere.iec.backend.aop.domain`: this package contains data model classes.

Figure 10: structure of domain package

- `com.piacere.iec.backend.repository`: this package contains Spring Data SQL repository classes.
- `com.piacere.iec.backend.security`: this package contains Spring Security related classes for security management.
- `com.piacere.iec.backend.service`: this package contains iec-backend services for CRUD operations and other requirements needed.
- `com.piacere.iec.backend.web`: this package contains classes to expose iec-backend rest end points.

6.1.2 IEC-Frontend

The main structure of the prototype developed in this first stage of the project is composed of JAVA classes related to Spring boot project and AngularJS files.

6.1.2.1 Spring boot package information

Figure 11: relation of packages

Each of these packages has its main objective and its context within the whole prototype. Furthermore, these packages are also comprised by several JAVA classes. With all this, the main purpose and composition of each component is as follows:

- `com.piacere.iec.frontend.aop.logging`: This package is composed by `LoggingAspect.java` which define the aspect for logging execution of service and repository Spring components.
- `com.piacere.iec.frontend.config`: This package contains all classes related to configuration purposes.
- `com.piacere.iec.frontend.domain`: This package contains user data model and Authority classes.
- `com.piacere.iec.frontend.repository`: This package contains Spring Data SQL repository classes for user and security management.
- `com.piacere.iec.frontend.security`: This package contains Spring Security related classes for security management.
- `com.piacere.iec.frontend.service`: This package contains iec-frontend services for CRUD operations and other requirements needed for user and security management.
- `com.piacere.iec.frontend.web`: This package contains classes to expose iec-frontend rest end points for user and security management.

6.1.2.2 AngularJS package information

Figure 12: AngularJS package

Each of these packages and typescript files has its main objective and its context within the whole prototype.

The main purpose and composition of each file/component is as follows:

- `app/app.constants.ts`: Global application constants.
- `app/app.module.ts`: Declaration of all the needed modules, providers and components loaded in the web application.
- `app/app-routing.module.ts`: Routing configuration.
- `app/account`: Account management module. It contains components and services related to the user account management.
- `app/admin`: Admin related modules. Api documentation module, Gateway route module and user management module.
- `app/config`: Global configuration and constant typescript files.
- `app/core`: Global utils files, core models and services.
- `app/entities/iecBackend`: All files related to the iecBackend data model. Services, components and models.
- `app/home`: Home component
- `app/layout`: Layout components; error, footer, navbar, main and profile components.
- `app/login`: User Login component.
- `app/shared`: Shared module with common components, directives and pipes.
- `content`: Static files of webapp. Css and images.
- `i18n`: Internationalization files.

6.2 Installation instructions

This project is executed in a docker container. There are docker compose files for each environment development/production. To execute this project in a development environment:

1. Clone repository
`git clone https://git.code.tecnalia.com/piacere/public/the-platform/iop/iec-catalogue.git`
2. Run docker compose to start Jhipster registry and MySQL instances
`docker-compose --env-file .env.dev -f docker-compose-local-dev.yaml up --build -dFrontends`
3. Build and deploy Catalogue backend
`./mvnw -Pdev,api-docs -DskipTests`
4. Build and deploy Catalogue frontend
`./mvnw -Pdev,webapp,api-docs -DskipTests`

Available services after initialization (User with admin role: admin / admin; User with non-admin role: user / user):

Once we successfully deploy the docker-compose, and supposing the following values for SERVER_HOST (192.168.56.1.nip.io) and HTTPS_PORT (8443) we will be able to access the services at:

- <https://iec.192.168.56.1.nip.io:8443/> IEC for development
- <https://iec.192.168.56.1.nip.io:8443/services/iecbkend/v3/api-docs> IEC API

And to those generic services described at development-services:

- <https://traefik.192.168.56.1.nip.io:8443/> Traefik dashboard
- <https://traefik.192.168.56.1.nip.io:8443/api/http/routers> Traefik API
- <https://portainer.192.168.56.1.nip.io:8443/> to access Portainer
- <https://ca.192.168.56.1.nip.io:8443/> Tecnalia CA

Apart from those, in case we are using the ".env.int" we will have access to additional endpoints

- <https://jhipster-registry.192.168.56.1.nip.io:8443/> jhipster registry

6.3 User Manual

The catalogue is not intended to be used directly by the user. It is part of the optimization component and is used behind the scenes (mainly by the IOP) to calculate and provide its results. This use is made via the APIs provided by the IEC and is transparent for the final user.

However, the Catalogue provides a GUI (Graphical User Interface) that allows to check its contents and interact with it. Also, the integrated PIACERE IDE offers a way of show the content of the catalogue in a specific view.

A set of Gherkin notation-based scenarios have been defined to ease the usage and validation of the IEC by the uses cases. These are included in Appendix C.

6.3.1 Using the catalogue via webpage

The home page of the Catalogue shows a table of the number of services contained, organized by providers (files) and service types (rows):

The screenshot shows the Piacere IEC v0.0.1-SNAPSHOT welcome page. The page title is "Welcome to Piacere IEC!" with the subtitle "Infrastructural Elements Catalogue". A green notification bar states "You are logged in as user 'admin'". Below this is a table showing the number of services for each provider (CloudSigma, OpenStack, Google, Azure, Arsys, Amazon, AIMS) across three service types: Database, Storage, and Virtual Machine.

	CloudSigma	OpenStack	Google	Azure	Arsys	Amazon	AIMES
Database	0 service(s)	0 service(s)	2 service(s)	2 service(s)	0 service(s)	4 service(s)	0 service(s)
Storage	0 service(s)	0 service(s)	2 service(s)	3 service(s)	4 service(s)	2 service(s)	0 service(s)
Virtual Machine	1 service(s)	5 service(s)	2 service(s)	6 service(s)	9 service(s)	11 service(s)	0 service(s)

At the bottom of the page, there is a European Union logo and text: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101000162." The TecNALIA logo is also present with the tagline "Inspiring Business". Copyright information for 2021 is provided with a link to https://www.piacere-project.eu/.

Figure 13: Welcome page of IEC.

The Service Classes option lists the types of services contained in the Catalogue:

The screenshot shows the "Service Classes" page in the Piacere IEC v0.0.1-SNAPSHOT application. The page has a blue header with the title "Service Classes". Below the header is a table listing the service classes: Database, Storage, and Virtual Machine. Each row shows the name, a status indicator (Active), and a "View" button.

Name	Status	Action
Database	Active	View
Storage	Active	View
Virtual Machine	Active	View

Figure 14: Service Classes page of IEC.

Clicking the "View" button shows the attributes of the selected type of service.

Figure 15: View Service Classes page of the IEC.

The “Services” menu option list all the services in the catalogue. A search box allows to filter by the name of the service.

Figure 16: Services page of IEC.

A click on the “View” button of one of the services shows its properties:

Figure 17: View Service page of IEC.

While a click on the “Edit” button of the service allows to edit its properties:

Figure 18: Edit Service page of IEC.

Finally, the “instances” menu option shows a list of instances of the deployed services:

Deployment ID	Name	Status	Instance Ip Url	Email	Service	N.Alerts	
deployment02	instanceTest2	Active	168.0.1.102	testmail2@tecnalia.com	db.mysql.G	3	View Edit Delete
Id02	Test2	Active	168.0.1.102	testmail@tecnalia.com	C4_USA	0	View Edit Delete

Showing 1 - 2 of 2 items.

Figure 19: instances page of IEC.

6.3.2 Using the Catalogue from the IDE

Prior to using the Catalogue itself, you need to open the right view.

1. We use the “Window” toolbar menu, click on “Show view” option and select the “PIACERE Infrastructure Elements Catalogue” option.

Figure 20: Show view option in the IDE.

2. Once in the view, the different types of elements of the Catalogue are shown in a list.

Figure 21: Catalogue View.

3. Clicking in any of these types, all the services of the type are listed (a further click in any of the services shown its properties and values).

Figure 22: List of services of Databases type.

6.4 Licensing information

This component is offered under Apache 2.0 license. More detailed information can be found in the GitLab repository.

6.5 Download

The code is available at the public GitLab repository of the PIACERE project:

<https://git.code.tecnalia.com/piacere/public/the-platform/iop/iec-catalogue>

7 IOP Optimizer Delivery and usage

7.1 Package information

The main structure of the IOP Optimizer has been substantially modified in comparison to the first prototype shown in the previous version of this deliverable. We show in the following Figure 23 the structure of that v1.

Figure 23: Main structure of the developed first prototype.

Each of these packages had a principal objective in the context of the prototype, which clearly had an academic oriented purpose. Thus, the purposes of each package were as follows:

- `algorithm.runner`: this package was composed by two different classes, which act as the main entry point of the system.
- `data_reader`: this component was comprised by one sole class with has the goal of acceding the IEC for obtaining the information needed for conducting the optimization.
- `jmetal.continuous`: this package contained the jMetal implementations of some important multi/many-objective algorithms contemplated in the first prototype of the PIACERE IOP Optimizer. In overall, 12 different algorithms were adapted, including the NSGA-II, MOCcell, SPEA2 or the SMPSO among others. Additionally, approaches within this package defined the optimization variables as `double` values.
- `jmetal.discrete`: this component contained the discrete jMetal implementations of some important multi/many-objective algorithms. In this case, 9 different algorithms were adapted to the PIACERE optimization problem, dealing it with `integer` values. Among the considered algorithms, NSGAI, MOMBI2, SMSEMOA and NSGAI can be found.
- `moea.algorithm`: this package included the solvers embracing the MOEA framework. In this case, algorithms were able to solve the problem using `continuous` and `discrete` variables. For the first prototype of the IOP, 12 different solvers were adapted, including alternatives such as NSGAI, OMOPSO, VEGA, MOEAD or GDE3.
- `problems`: this package was comprised by six classes, which were the ones in charge of modelling the optimization problem, specifying the optimizing variables of the problem, their associated constraints, defining the objective function and calculating the value of each of the considered optimizing objectives.
- `util`: this last package contained two different classes which main purpose is to gather the results obtained by each algorithm and return them to the user in an understandable form.

In the second version of the IOP Optimizer, this structure has been fully modified. Two are the main reasons that have: *i)* include all the mechanisms for making the IOP accessible for external PIACERE components and *ii)* transform the academic-oriented first prototype to a more use case-oriented approach.

With all this, we depict in the following figure the current structure of the IOP Optimizer in its second version.

Figure 24: Main structure of the developed first prototype

For analysing this whole prototype, we will divide the explanation into two thematic groups: the first one dedicated with the packages oriented to the IOP optimization problem solving (Section 7.1.1), and the other one dedicated to those packages created for making the whole IOP accessible for external components (Section 7.1.2)

7.1.1 Packages related with the optimization problem solving

The main role of the packages that fall within this category is to solve the PIACERE optimization problem described in Section 3. For doing that, some of the classes that form the first prototype have been modified, others have been removed and many of them have been reallocated in new created packages.

Probably, the most representative examples are the packages now coined as `com.piacere.iop.optimizer.algorithm.jmetal.continuous` and `com.piacere.iop.optimizer.algorithm.jmetal.discrete`. These packages are the same previously known as `jmetal.continuous` and `jmetal.discrete`, respectively. We depict in the next Figure 25 the composition of these both packages.

Figure 25: Composition of the packages that contain the jMetal algorithm adaptations

Essentially, these packages contain the jMetal implementations of the algorithms contemplated in the first prototype. On this regard, it should be taken into account that the algorithm that has been finally used for the second version of the tool, and the one that is going to be employed for solving the PIACERE use cases is the `NSGAIIDiscreteOptRunner.java`, in its discrete variant. In any case, the rest of the algorithms have been left on their corresponding packages for future additional performance testing purposes.

Regarding the classes that define the optimization problem itself, with all the new particularities detailed in Section 3. For doing that, the newly created `com.piacere.iop.optimizer.problems` package has been created, containing four of the JAVA classes that comprised the previously coined as `problem` package. In this new package, the four classes regarding the jMetal adaptation of the problem have been considered, eliminating those classes that refer to the MOEA framework, which has not been considered for this second version of the tool.

Figure 26: composition of the `com.piacere.iop.optimizer.problems` package

Regarding the output of the results, the class in charge of this crucial aspect is the one coined as `IOPSolutionLustOutput.java`, which is the same as in the previous first prototype. In any case, as commented in D5.7, this class has been significantly modified in order to adapt the output of the IOP to the needs of the project. For this reason, the output that this class has been adapted to the DOML format, in order to provide the outcome as depicted in Section 3.1.2.5 and 3.1.2.6. As shown in Figure 27, `IOPSolutionListOutput.java` is now contained in a newly created `com.piacere.iop.optimizer.util` package.

Figure 27: structure of the `com.piacere.iop.optimizer.util` package

Finally, the last of the packages dedicated to the optimization problem solving, is the one coined as `com.piacere.iop.optimizer.service`. This package contains three different classes of a crucial importance for the correct working of the IOP component. In Figure 28 we depict the composition of this newly created package:

Figure 28: Composition of the package `com.piacere.iop.optimizer.service`

Going deeper on this package, each of the classes that comprise it have the following role within the whole IOP Optimizer:

- `CatalogService`: This class is specifically dedicated to access the IEC for obtaining all the elements and their features for being used for the optimization procedure. Thus, this class deals with all the security aspects needed for acceding the IEC through the JAVA code.
- `DataReaderService`: Once the data is obtained in its raw form, this `DataReaderService` class is in charge of reading all the information and transform it in optimization variables. This class has also some filtering methods, in order to properly contemplate optimization requirements related, for example, with the region or the provider.
- `OptimizerService`: this class is, probably, the most important one of the whole IOP Optimizer. `OptimizerService.java` is the main class, which orchestrates all the optimization process. This is the entry point of the IOP for both of its execution ways: from the JAVA code or as external service, and it is in charge of receiving the DOML inserted as input and starting the complete pipeline of execution of the IOP. After all the optimization is executed, this class is also the one that returns to the user the main outcome provided by the internal class `IOPSolutionLustOutput.java`.

7.1.2 Packages dedicated to make the whole IOP accessible

The packages dedicated to providing the IOP functionality are, in most of cases, generated using Jhipster. In Figure 29 we depict the packages of the IOP, most of them, except those indicated with (1), have been automatically generated based on the initial configuration of the Jhipster. Besides, most of the customization for the service provision is implemented in (2), where the request is received and the jMetal packages are used.

Figure 29: packages generated by jhipster.

Besides, there are some other packages manipulated in order to declare, expose and characterize the IOP services. These are `com.piacere.iop.optimizer.web.rest` and `com.piacere.iop.optimizer.security`.

In the first one, we declare the endpoint and the data received and the response sent. The second one the package that allow us to manage the access security together with the YAML configuration of the service. The configuration allows us to define multiple mechanism to specify who can or who cannot access the service. i.e. json web token (JWT), Open ID, etc.

Jhipster users yeoman to generate the microservice elements the configuration used to the generation is stored in `.yo-rc.json`. This is useful in case we want to regenerate the microservice from scratch or update to a newer version of Jhipster that will help us to keep our microservice with the latest libraries that include the latest security patches.

7.2 Installation instructions

The installation instructions for this second version of the tool are similar to the ones provided for the first version of the IOP Optimizer. The whole tool is built in a compressed folder, which can be imported by any JAVA development framework such as NetBeans or Eclipse. Furthermore, the project can also be imported as a Maven project, being this option even more comfortable than just importing the whole project folder. Related also with this last aspect, jMetal framework is imported to the project and used by the IOP using Maven functionality.

Additionally, the last version of the jMetal framework has been used for this second version of the IOP, which at the time of writing this deliverable, is version 5.1. Regarding the MOEA optimization framework, which was considered in the first version of the prototype, it has been finally discarded from the project as described in previous Section 5.3.3. for this reason, it is not necessary to include it in the `pom.xml` related to the project.

Finally, we depict the dependencies added to the `pom.xml` file for correctly importing jMetal framework to the JAVA project.

```
<dependency>
  <groupId>org.uma.jmetal</groupId>
  <artifactId>jmetal-core</artifactId>
  <version>5.1</version>
</dependency>

<dependency>
  <groupId>org.uma.jmetal</groupId>
  <artifactId>jmetal-problem</artifactId>
  <version>5.1</version>
</dependency>

<dependency>
  <groupId>org.uma.jmetal</groupId>
  <artifactId>jmetal-algorithm</artifactId>
  <version>5.1</version>
</dependency>

<dependency>
  <groupId>org.uma.jmetal</groupId>
  <artifactId>jmetal-exec</artifactId>
  <version>5.1</version>
</dependency>
```

7.3 User Manual

Three different alternatives are available for properly testing the IOP Optimizer. The first one resorts to the execution of the JAVA project using a JAVA framework and a unitary test. The second alternative is related to using it through the Eclipse based IDE, developed in the context of PIACERE project. Finally, the IOP can also be run via webpage-based platform. These three methods are explained in this Section.

7.3.1 Running the IOP Optimizer via JAVA code

The entry point of the IOP Optimizer if the user wants to run it via JAVA code is the class named as `OptimizerServiceIT.java`, which is part of the package `com.piacere.iop.optimizer.service`, within the test branch of the code. We depict in the following figure an excerpt of the class `OptimizerServiceIT.java`. More concretely, we show the part of the code in which the IOP is called through the `optimizedService.run(call)` method.

```
@Test
void testDefaultOptimize() throws Exception {

    String call = "...";
    String result = optimizerService.run(call);
    System.out.println(result);
    assertThat("ok").isEqualTo("ok");
}
}
```

Figure 30: An excerpt of the `OptimizerServiceIT.java` class

As mentioned, the method that runs the IOP is the one coined as `optimizedService.run(call)`. This is the method that it is called by the PIACERE components to make the IOP run and to find the most optimized deployment configurations. Two different important aspects can be seen in this little excerpt of code:

- For properly run the Optimizer, a String should be introduced as input (represented as `call` in Figure 30). As explained before, this input should be a fully working DOML file, formatted as String, in which the `optimization opt` (see Section 3.1.2) part should be correctly introduced. As mentioned, this `optimization opt` part must have the following format:

```
optimization opt {
    objectives {
    }
    nonfunctional_requirements {
    }
}
```

In which `objectives` contains the optimization objectives (such as cost, performance or availability) and `nonfunctional_requirements` slot includes main optimization requirements (such as the maximum cost, the minimum performance or the elements to search). For further information on this aspect, we recall Sections 3.1.2.1, 3.1.2.2, 3.1.2.3 and 3.1.2.4.

- The output of the IOP is a String (represented as `result` in Figure 30), which is the same DOML introduced as input (`call` variable in Figure 30). In a nutshell, the output string introduces the main results as an adding in the `optimization opt` section of the input DOML, following this format:

```
solution solX {
    objectives {

    }
    Decisions[]
}
```

It should be considered that one solution excerpt is introduced by each of the solutions found by the Optimizer. More concretely, this solution part includes an `objectives` part representing the main values for each optimization objective introduced in the input DOML, and a `Decisions` part, which represents the solution itself, that is, the elements chosen from the IEC and which built the deployment configuration. For further information on this aspect, we recommend readers to go back to Section 3.1.2.5 and 3.1.2.6.

For extending the information here depicted, we have shown in Appendix B a possible DOML example that can be used as input for the `optimizedService.run(call)`. The example depicted in the appendix (which should substitute `String call = "..."` line of Figure 30) is based on a test instance provided by Prodevelop, and it is inspired by their use case.

7.3.2 Running the IOP Optimizer via PIACERE IDE

In addition to executing the code as mentioned in previous section, the IOP can also be used through the PIACERE IDE, developed in the context of this project. In this sense, the IOP Optimizer is completely integrated with this tool. We introduce in Appendix A two different scenarios that a user can follow in order to test the IOP Optimizer following this second running procedure.

7.3.3 Running the IOP Optimizer via OpenAPI

In case we want to execute the IOP optimizer by its OpenAPI specification we have several options, some of them are:

- We can get the OpenAPI specification and import in a testing tool such as Postman
- We can use the API explorer tool in IEC, <https://iec.ci.piacere.digital.tecnalia.dev/admin/docs>
- We can use any swagger explorer providing a proper CORS configuration.

First step is how to get the OpenAPI specification that describes the IOP service following and standardized syntax. In order to get the OpenAPI specification, we use the same component that as part of the basic features provided by Jhipster, so we can retrieve the Jhipster specification. Thus, to get the specification we can access an endpoint in the IOP, for example: <https://iop.ci.piacere.digital.tecnalia.dev/v3/api-docs>.

This file can be used in any of the methods specified before. Figure 31 shows how the URL is used to import the IOP OpenAPI in Postman.

Figure 31: Postman link import

Figure 32 shows how the API looks like in postman after importing.

Figure 32: IOP Optimizer API after import

Finally, Figure 33 shows how the IOP API looks like in the IEC Administration API tool.

The screenshot displays the Swagger UI for the iopOptimizer API. The browser address bar shows the URL 'iec.ci.piacere.digital.tecnalia.dev/admin/docs'. The Swagger UI header includes the Swagger logo, 'Select a definition' dropdown set to 'iopoptimizer', and the API title 'iopOptimizer API 0.0.1 OAS3'. Below the title, it shows the path '/services/iopoptimizer/v3/api-docs', 'iopOptimizer API documentation', and 'unlicensed'. A 'Servers' dropdown is set to '/services/iopoptimizer - added by global filter'. A 'Filter by tag' input field is present. The 'optimizer' tag is selected, showing a 'POST /api/optimize optimize' endpoint with a 'VALID' button.

Figure 33: IOP Optimizer API in the Administration API tool in IEC.

7.4 Licensing information

This component is offered under Apache 2.0 license. Detailed information can be found in the GitLab repository.

7.5 Download

The code is available at the public GitLab repository of the PIACERE project:

<https://git.code.tecnalia.com/piacere/public/the-platform/iop/optimizer>

8 Conclusions

This manuscript has been devoted to describing the second version of the IOP, composed by the Infrastructural Elements Catalogue and the IOP Optimizer. On the one hand, the IEC in PIACERE stores the main features about the services available at service providers, and also the instances of each of these services being used by the different application being deployed by the PIACERE infrastructure.

On the other hand, the IOP Optimizer employs multi-objective metaheuristics for finding optimized deployment configurations of the IaC, resorting to the most appropriated infrastructural elements. Of course, this matchmaking should consider the main needs of the user, i.e., her/his requirements and constraints. Thus, the IOP will success if the deployment configuration provided are good enough for meeting the users' requirements and needs. To this end, several deployment configurations will be shown and ranked using one of the objectives as ranking reference.

In this second version of the deliverable, we have described the preliminarily modelled optimization problem, as well as the main improvements developed in the second year of the project for correctly adapting this problem to the use cases' real needs. Furthermore, we have described how both the IEC and IOP Optimizer have evolved between M12 and M24. As explained before, regarding the Optimizer, this work has been focused on the adaptation of the IOP first prototype, which was clearly an academic-oriented prototype, to the use-case oriented version of the IOP. This mature version of the IOP is DOML compliant, and it is able to attend the user needs, providing optimized solutions based on user's requirements. Thanks to the work conducted in the second year of the project, the integration of both the IOP and the IEC into the PIACERE IDE has been already done, and it has also been preliminarily tested on use cases, providing a satisfactory performance.

Further work contemplates, on the one hand, the development of a more advanced IEC including a wider set of services with some automatic updates and the dynamic information of monitored instances and, on the other hand, the final adaptation of the IOP to the use cases, a more detailed research-oriented experimentation, and the implementation of improvement mechanisms in the selected optimization method.

9 References

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10 Appendix A. IOP Scenarios

In this appendix, we depict two different specific scenarios for using the IOP.

Scenario: IOP, Minimizing the cost, maximizing the availability and the performance. Two VM and two DB to deploy, with two requirements (KR9) [Scenario 1]

Given A verified DOML document

In this first scenario, I want to optimize three different objectives: minimize the cost, maximize the availability and maximize the availability. The elements that I want to deploy are two databases and two virtual machines. I want to rank the solutions using the cost as reference. Additionally, I have some two requirements. I want that the overall deployment cost does not overpass 500 dollars, and I want the overall availability to be more than 96. For this reason, in the last part of my verified DOML, I add the following content:

```
optimization opt {
  objectives {
    "cost" => min
    "performance" => max
    "availability" => max
  }
  nonfunctional_requirements {
    req1 "Cost <= 500" max 500.0 => "cost";
    req2 "Availability >= 96.0%" min 96.0 => "availability";
    req3 "elements" => "DB, DB, VM, VM";
  }
}
```

And the user has already introduced the optimization objectives and requirements

When user navigates to the DOML document,

And right-click on the file

And selects "Optimise"

Then The IOP is invoked

And runs the optimisation algorithm

And returns the optimised IaC examples

The IOP returns the same input DOML, but with the optimization results added. In the optimization opt section, the solutions are added.

```
optimization opt {
  objectives {
    "cost" => min
    "performance" => max
    "availability" => max
  }
  nonfunctional_requirements {
    req1 "Cost <= 500.0" max 500.0 => "cost";
    req2 "Availability >= 96.0%" min 96.0 => "availability";
```

```

req3 "elements" => "DB, DB, VM, VM";
}
solution sol2 {
objectives {
cost 198.0 euro
performance 40.0 metric
availability 98.35 %
}
decisions ["[db.dynamo.4, db.m3.medium, C4_Europe, m1.small]"]
}
solution sol3 {
objectives {
cost 228.0 euro
performance 38.0 metric
availability 98.5 %
}
decisions ["[db.m3.medium, db.dynamo.3, C4_Europe, C2_UnitedKingdom]"]
}
}

```

Furthermore, in the concretization section, the information about the elements of each solution is shown.

And the user evaluates and verifies the output results

Scenario: IOP: Minimizing the cost, maximizing the availability. Three VM to deploy with three requirements (KR9) [Scenario 2]

Given A verified DOML document

In this second scenario, I want to optimize two different objectives: minimize the cost, and maximize the availability. The elements that I want to deploy are three virtual machines. I want to rank the solutions using the cost as reference. Additionally, I have some requirements. I want that the overall deployment cost does not overpass 400 dollars, and I want the overall performance to be more than 10. Furthermore, I want all the element to be deployed in Europe For this reason, in the last part of my verified DOML, I add the following content:

```

optimization opt {
objectives {
"cost" => min
"availability" => max
}
nonfunctional_requirements {
req1 "Cost <= 400" max 400.0 => "cost";
req2 "Region" values "00EU" => "region";
}
}

```

```

req3 "Performance >= 10.0%" min 10.0 => "performance";
req4 "elements" => "VM, VM, VM";
}
}

```

And the user has already introduced the optimization objectives and requirements

When user navigates to the DOML document,

And right-click on the file

And selects "Optimise"

Then The IOP is invoked

And runs the optimisation algorithm

And returns the optimised IaC examples

The IOP returns the same input DOML, but with the optimization results added. In the optimization opt section, the solutions are added.

```

optimization opt {
  objectives {
    "cost" => min
    "availability" => max
  }
  nonfunctional_requirements {
    req1 "Cost <= 400.0" max 400.0 => "cost";
    req2 "Region" values "00EU" => "region";
    req3 "Performance >= 10.0%" min 10.0 => "performance";
    req4 "elements" => "VM, VM, VM";
  }
  solution sol2 {
    objectives {
      cost 39.53 euro
      availability 98.83333333333333 %
    }
    decisions ["[C1_Spain, m1.small, t2.nano]"]
  }
  solution sol3 {
    objectives {
      cost 59.53 euro
      availability 99.03333333333335 %
    }
    decisions ["[C1_Spain, C2_UnitedKingdom, t2.nano]"]
  }
}

```

Furthermore, in the concretization section, the information about the elements of each solution is shown.

And the user evaluates and verifies the output results

11 Appendix B. IOP input example

In order to complete the information about the IOP Optimizer and how to call the service, here we depict one input example for running the IOP following the procedure described in 7.3.1.

```
String call = "dom1 posidonia\n"
+ "properties {\n"
+ "  entorno=\"pre\";\n"
+ "  proyecto=\"balears\";\n"
+ "}\n"
+ "\n"
+ "// Application Definition\n"
+ "application posidonia {\n"
+ "  software_component Gestaut {\n"
+ "    provides { http https }\n"
+ "    consumes { dbAccess, search }\n"
+ "  }\n"
+ "  software_component ElasticSearch {\n"
+ "    provides { search }\n"
+ "    consumes { dbAccess }\n"
+ "  }\n"
+ "  software_component Edi {\n"
+ "    provides { edi }\n"
+ "    consumes { dbAccess }\n"
+ "  }\n"
+ "  dbms Database {\n"
+ "    provides {\n"
+ "      dbAccess\n"
+ "    }\n"
+ "  }\n"
+ "}\n"
+ "\n"
+ "infrastructure abstractInfra {\n"
+ "  // Networks\n"
+ "  net vpc {\n"
+ "    address \"10.100.0.0/16\"\n"
+ "    protocol \"tcp/ip\"\n"
+ "    // TODO: simplify syntax: (nested subnets, net) -> subnet sn1
{...}\n"
+ "    subnets{\n"
+ "      net subnet1 {\n"
+ "        // ---\n"
+ "        address \"10.100.1.0/24\"\n"
+ "        protocol \"tcp/ip\"\n"
+ "      }\n"
+ "      net subnet2 {\n"
+ "        address \"10.100.2.0/24\"\n"
+ "        protocol \"tcp/ip\"\n"
+ "      }\n"
+ "      net subnet3 {\n"
+ "        address \"10.100.3.0/24\"\n"
+ "        protocol \"tcp/ip\"\n"
+ "      }\n"
+ "    }\n"
+ "  }\n"
+ "  // Credentials\n"
+ "  // TODO: key file?\n"
+ "  key_pair GestautKeyName {\n"
+ "    algorithm \"RSA\"\n"
+ "    bits 4096\n"
+ "  }\n"
+ "  key_pair ESKeyName {\n"
+ "    algorithm \"RSA\"\n"
+ "    bits 4096\n"
+ "  }\n"
+ "}
```

```

+ " key_pair EdiKeyName {\n"
+ "     algorithm \"RSA\"\n"
+ "     bits 4096\n"
+ " }\n"
+ " user_pass dbCredentials {\n"
+ "     user \"balearesadm\"\n"
+ "     pass \"balearesadm\"\n"
+ " }\n"
+ " \n"
+ " // Nodes\n"
+ " vm OracleDB {\n"
+ "     iface db1 {\n"
+ "         belongs_to subnet1\n"
+ "     }\n"
+ "     iface db2 {\n"
+ "         belongs_to subnet2\n"
+ "     }\n"
+ "     iface db3 {\n"
+ "         belongs_to subnet3\n"
+ "     }\n"
+ "     sto \"20\"\n"
+ "     credentials dbCredentials\n"
+ " }\n"
+ " \n"
+ " vm_image posidonia_image {\n"
+ "     generates gestaut_vm, elasticsearch_vm, edi_vm\n"
+ "     image \"ami-02a6bfdcf8224bd77\"\n"
+ " }\n"
+ " \n"
+ " autoscale_group gestaut_asg {\n"
+ "     // TODO: Shouldn't vm live outside the group leaving a
reference here? vm might also be referenced by other components.\n"
+ "     // It also applies to the following vms in other groups.\n"
+ "     vm gestaut_vm {\n"
+ "         credentials GestautKeyName\n"
+ "     }\n"
+ "     min 1\n"
+ "     max 1 // Using AutoScaleGroup as a way to automatically reboot
a machine in case of error\n"
+ "     network vpc\n"
+ " }\n"
+ " \n"
+ " autoscale_group elasticsearch_asg {\n"
+ "     // TODO\n"
+ "     vm elasticsearch_vm {\n"
+ "         credentials ESKeyName\n"
+ "     }\n"
+ "     min 1\n"
+ "     max 1 // Using AutoScaleGroup as a way to automatically reboot
a machine in case of error\n"
+ "     network vpc\n"
+ " }\n"
+ " \n"
+ " autoscale_group edi_asg {\n"
+ "     // TODO\n"
+ "     vm edi_vm {\n"
+ "         credentials EdiKeyName\n"
+ "     }\n"
+ "     min 1\n"
+ "     max 1 // Using AutoScaleGroup as a way to automatically reboot
a machine in case of error\n"
+ "     network vpc\n"
+ " }\n"
+ " \n"
+ " security_group sg {\n"

```

```

+ " // TODO: the following vms should have the associated
interfaces (ifaces) in the security group?\n"
+ " //nodes gestaut_vm, elasticsearch_vm, edi_vm\n"
+ " egress salida {\n"
+ "     protocol \"-1"\n"
+ "     from_port 0\n"
+ "     to_port 0\n"
+ "     cidr [\"0.0.0.0/0\"]\n"
+ " }\n"
+ " ingress lb {\n"
+ "     protocol \"tcp\"\n"
+ "     from_port 80\n"
+ "     to_port 80\n"
+ "     cidr [\"10.100.1.0/24\", \"10.100.2.0/24\",
\"10.100.3.0/24\"]\n"
+ " }\n"
+ " ingress es {\n"
+ "     protocol \"tcp\"\n"
+ "     from_port 9200\n"
+ "     to_port 9200\n"
+ "     cidr [\"10.100.1.0/24\", \"10.100.2.0/24\",
\"10.100.3.0/24\"]\n"
+ " }\n"
+ " ingress monitor {\n"
+ "     protocol \"tcp\"\n"
+ "     from_port 6556\n"
+ "     to_port 6556\n"
+ "     cidr [\"54.217.119.81/32\"]\n"
+ " }\n"
+ "\n"
+ " // TODO: ftp (20/21) or ssh (22)?\n"
+ " ingress ftp {\n"
+ "     protocol \"tcp\"\n"
+ "     from_port 22\n"
+ "     to_port 22\n"
+ "     cidr [\"213.96.27.139/32\", \"37.187.173.88/32\",
\"51.89.40.59/32\", \"195.53.242.200/32\"]\n"
+ " }\n"
+ " }\n"
+ " \n"
+ " security_group dbsg {\n"
+ " // TODO: the associated vms and ifaces?\n"
+ " egress salida {\n"
+ "     protocol \"-1"\n"
+ "     from_port 0\n"
+ "     to_port 0\n"
+ "     cidr [\"0.0.0.0/0\"]\n"
+ " }\n"
+ " ingress ora {\n"
+ "     protocol \"tcp\"\n"
+ "     from_port 1521\n"
+ "     to_port 1521\n"
+ "     cidr [\"10.100.1.0/24\", \"10.100.2.0/24\",
\"10.100.3.0/24\", \"84.124.78.66/32\"]\n"
+ " }\n"
+ " }\n"
+ " \n"
+ " security_group elbgs {\n"
+ " // TODO: the associated vms and ifaces?\n"
+ " egress salida {\n"
+ "     protocol \"-1"\n"
+ "     from_port 0\n"
+ "     to_port 0\n"
+ "     cidr [\"0.0.0.0/0\"]\n"
+ " }\n"
+ " ingress http {\n"

```

```

+ "          protocol \"tcp\"\\n\"
+ "          from_port 80\\n\"
+ "          to_port 80\\n\"
+ "          cidr [\"0.0.0.0/0\", \"::/0\"]\\n\"
+ "        }\\n\"
+ "      ingress https {\\n\"
+ "        protocol \"tcp\"\\n\"
+ "        from_port 443\\n\"
+ "        to_port 443\\n\"
+ "        cidr [\"0.0.0.0/0\", \"::/0\"]\\n\"
+ "      }\\n\"
+ "      ingress es {\\n\"
+ "        protocol \"tcp\"\\n\"
+ "        from_port 9200\\n\"
+ "        to_port 9200\\n\"
+ "        cidr [\"10.100.1.0/24\", \"10.100.2.0/24\",
+ \"10.100.3.0/24\"]\\n\"
+ "      }\\n\"
+ "    }\\n\"
+ "  \\n\"
+ "  security_group checkmk {\\n\"
+ "    // TODO: the associated vms and ifaces?\\n\"
+ "    egress salida {\\n\"
+ "      protocol \"-1\"\\n\"
+ "      from_port 0\\n\"
+ "      to_port 0\\n\"
+ "      cidr [\"0.0.0.0/0\"]\\n\"
+ "    }\\n\"
+ "    ingress http {\\n\"
+ "      protocol \"tcp\"\\n\"
+ "      from_port 80\\n\"
+ "      to_port 80\\n\"
+ "      cidr [\"84.124.78.66/32\"]\\n\"
+ "    }\\n\"
+ "    ingress https {\\n\"
+ "      protocol \"tcp\"\\n\"
+ "      from_port 443\\n\"
+ "      to_port 443\\n\"
+ "      cidr [\"84.124.78.66/32\"]\\n\"
+ "    }\\n\"
+ "  \\n\"
+ "    // TODO: ftp (20/21) or ssh (22)?\\n\"
+ "    ingress ftp {\\n\"
+ "      protocol \"tcp\"\\n\"
+ "      from_port 22\\n\"
+ "      to_port 22\\n\"
+ "      cidr [\"84.124.78.66/32\"]\\n\"
+ "    }\\n\"
+ "  }\\n\"
+ "  \\n\"
+ "  deployment dep {\\n\"
+ "    Gestaut -> gestaut_vm,\\n\"
+ "    ElasticSearch -> elasticsearch_vm,\\n\"
+ "    Edi -> edi_vm,\\n\"
+ "    Database -> OracleDB\\n\"
+ "  }\\n\"
+ "  active deployment dep\\n\"
+ "  \\n\"
+ "  // Concretization to AWS\\n\"
+ "  concretizations {\\n\"
+ "    concrete_infrastructure dev {\\n\"
+ "      provider aws {\\n\"
+ "        autoscale_group asg1 {\\n\"
+ "          maps elasticsearch_asg\\n\"

```

```

+ "                }\n"
+ "                autoscale_group asg2 {\n"
+ "                    maps edi_asg\n"
+ "                }\n"
+ "                autoscale_group asg3 {\n"
+ "                    maps gestaut_asg\n"
+ "                }\n"
+ "            }\n"
+ "        }\n"
+ "    }\n"
+ "    \n"
+ "    // concrete_infrastructure pro {\n"
+ "    //         provider aws {\n"
+ "    //             \n"
+ "    //         }\n"
+ "    //     }\n"
+ "    \n"
+ "    active dev\n"
+ "    }\n"
+ "    optimization opt {\n"
+ "    // objectives {\n"
+ "    //     \"cost\" => min\n"
+ "    //     \"availability\" => max\n"
+ "    //     }\n"
+ "    // nonfunctional_requirements {\n"
+ "    //     req1 \"Cost <= 1000\" max 1000.0 => \"cost\";\n"
+ "    //     req2 \"availability >= 90%\" min 90.0 => \"availability\";\n"
+ "    //     req3 \"elements\" => \"Storage, VM, VM, DB, VM\"\n"
+ "    //     }\n"
+ "    }\n"
+ "};

```

DRAFT

12 Appendix C. IEC Scenarios

The scenarios of IEC are described in this appendix.

FEATURE: PIACERE Design Time

Scenario: IOP working

Given the IOP need the Catalogue data to calculate optimizations

When the IOP invokes the IEC

Then the IEC returns the available elements in json format

FEATURE: PIACERE Run Time

Scenario: A project is being deployed

Given the deployment is successful

Then the PRC sends to the IEC the info about the deployed elements

And the IEC stores the information, including which service is deployed (type, id...)

And the IEC (periodically) connects to monitoring

And gets information about the deployed services

Scenario: A project is being undeployed

Given the un-deployment is successful

Then the PRC sends to the IEC the info about the deployed elements

And the IEC stores the information, including which service is undeployed (type, id...)

13 Appendix D. About Gaia-X

In its 2022 architecture document [4], the concepts in the scope of Gaia-X and their relations are described, that is, the Gaia-X conceptual model, shown in Figure 1. The Gaia-X core concepts are represented in classes. The upper part of the model shows different actors of Gaia-X (highlighted in blue), while the lower part shows elements of commercial trade and the relationship to actors outside Gaia-X.

Figure 34: Gaia-X Conceptual model [4]

A *Participant* can take on one or more of the following roles: *Provider*, *Consumer*, *Federator*. *Provider* and *Consumer* present the core roles that are in a business-to-business relationship while the *Federator* enables their interaction.

- A *Provider* is a *Participant* who provides Resources in the Gaia-X Ecosystem. The *Provider* defines the *Service Offering* including terms and conditions as well as technical Policies. Furthermore, it provides the *Service Instance* that includes a *Self-Description* and associated Policies.

- A *Consumer* is a Participant who searches Service Offerings and consumes Service Instances in the Gaia-X Ecosystem to enable digital offerings for End-Users.
- *Federators* are in charge of the Federation Services and the Federation which are independent of each other. Federators are Gaia-X Participants. There can be one or more Federators per type of Federation Service.
- A *Federation* refers to a loose set of interacting actors that directly or indirectly consume, produce, or provide related Resources.

Resources and Assets describe the goods and objects of a Gaia-X Ecosystem. Resources and Assets compose the Service Offerings.

An *Asset* can be a Data Asset, a Software Asset, a Node or an Interconnection Asset. A set of Policies described in a Self-Description is bound to each Asset. The different categories of Assets are shown in the following figure:

Figure 35: Assets categories [4]

- A *Data Asset* is an Asset that consists of data in any form and necessary information for data sharing.
- A *Node* is an Asset and represents a computational or physical entity that hosts, manipulates, or interacts with other computational or physical entities.
- A *Software Asset* is a form of Assets that consist of non-physical functions.
- An *Interconnection* as an Asset presents the connection between two or more Nodes. These Nodes are usually deployed in different infrastructure domains and owned by different stakeholders, such as Consumers and/or Providers. The Interconnection between the Nodes can be seen as a path which exhibits special characteristics, such as latency, bandwidth and security guarantees, that go beyond the characteristics of a path over the public Internet.

The difference between *Resources* and *Assets* lies in that Resources represent those elements necessary to supply Assets. In other words, they are internal Service Instances not available for order. For example, the running instance that provides a data set is a Resource.

Federation Services are services required for the operational implementation of a Gaia-X Data Ecosystem. They comprise four groups of services that are necessary to enable Federation of Resources, Participants and interactions between Ecosystems. The four service groups are Identity and Trust, Federated Catalogue, Sovereign Data Exchange and Compliance. The Federation Services provide the foundation for Service Offerings.

A *Service Offering* is defined as a set of Resources that a Provider aggregates and publishes as a single entry in a Catalogue. Service Offerings may themselves be aggregated realizing service

composition. The instantiation of a Service Offering is the deliverable of a Provider to a Consumer.

Federated Catalogue

The *Federated Catalogue* [4] constitutes an indexed repository of Gaia-X Self-Descriptions to enable the discovery and selection of Providers and their Service Offerings. The Self-Descriptions are the properties and Claims of Participants and Resources, representing key elements of transparency and trust in Gaia-X.

Self-Descriptions intended for public usage can be published in a Catalogue where they can be found by potential Consumers. The goal of Catalogues in Gaia-X is to enable Consumers to find best-matching offerings and to monitor for relevant changes of the offerings. The Providers decide in a self-sovereign manner which information they want to make public in a Catalogue and which information they only want to share privately.

A Catalogue stores Self-Descriptions both as standalone and as aggregated in a graph data structure. The Self-Description Storage contains the raw published Self-Description files (in the JSON-LD format). The individual Self-Descriptions can reference each other. The Self-Description Graph is the basis for advanced query mechanisms that consider the references between and among Self-Descriptions [4].

Ecosystem-specific Catalogues (e.g., for the automotive domain) and even company-internal Catalogues (with private Self-Descriptions to be used only internally) can be linked to the system of federated Catalogues. The Catalogue federation is used to exchange relevant Self-Descriptions and updates thereof. It is not used to execute queries in a distributed fashion [4].

The system of Federated Catalogues consists of a top-level Catalogue operated by Gaia-X and provides the means to link to Ecosystem-specific Catalogues (e.g., for the automotive domain) and even company-internal Catalogues with private Self-Descriptions to be used only internally. Self-Descriptions in a Catalogue are either loaded directly into a Catalogue or exchanged from another Catalogue through inter-Catalogue synchronization functions [4].

Since Self-Descriptions are protected by cryptographic signatures, they are immutable and cannot be changed once published. This implies that after any changes to a Self-Description, the Participant as the Self-Description issuer has to sign the Self-Description again and release it as a new version.

The possible states for the Self-Description lifecycle are four. All states except “Active” are terminal, which means that no further state transitions are allowed. The states are [4] [10]:

- **Active:** is the default state.
- **End-of-Life:** after a timeout date, e.g., the expiry of a cryptographic signature.
- **Deprecated:** by a newer Self-Description.
- **Revoked:** by the original issuer or a trusted party (e.g. because it contained wrong or fraudulent information).

The Self-Description Graph contains the information imported from the Self-Descriptions that are known to a Catalogue and in an "Active" state [10]. The Self-Description Graph allows for complex queries across Self-Descriptions. To present search results objectively and without discrimination, compliant Catalogues use a query engine with no internal ranking of results. Users can define filters and sort-criteria in their queries. But if some results have no unique ordering according to the defined sort-criteria, they are randomized. Self-Descriptions can be

communicated to the Catalogue by third parties, as the trust verification is independent of the distribution mechanism.

Self-Descriptions can be marked by the issuer as "private" to prevent them from being copied to a public Catalogue by a third party that received the Self-Description over a private channel [4]. The Catalogues have no built-in user interface, instead provide an API that can be used by an external user interface or technical clients [10]. The interfaces of the Gaia-X Federation Services use REST and the OpenAPI specification [11] to describe them.

A *Visitor* is an anonymous user accessing a Catalogue without a known account. Every Non-Visitor user interacts with a Catalogue REST API in the context of a session. Another option to interact with a Catalogue is to use a GUI frontend (e.g., a Gaia-X Portal or a custom GUI implementation) that uses a Catalogue REST API in the background. The interaction between a Catalogue and its GUI frontend is based on an authenticated session for the individual user of the GUI frontend.

Gaia-X Self-Descriptions express characteristics of Resources, Service Offerings and Participants that are linked to their respective Identifiers. Providers are responsible for the creation of Self-Descriptions of their Resources. In addition to self-declared Claims made by Participants, a Self-Description may comprise Credentials issued and signed by trusted parties. Self-Descriptions can be used for [4]:

- Discovery and composition of Service Offerings in a Catalogue
- Tool-assisted evaluation, integration and orchestration of Service Instances/Resources
- Enforcement, continuous validation and trust monitoring
- Negotiation of contractual terms concerning Resources of a Service Offering and Participants

Gaia-X Self-Descriptions are characterized by the following properties [4]:

- Machine-readable and machine-interpretable
- Technology-agnostic
- Adhering to a generalized schema with expressive semantics and validation rules
- Interoperable, following standards in terms of format, structure, and included expressions (semantics)
- Flexible, extensible and future-proof in that new properties can be easily added
- Navigable and referenceable from anywhere in a decentralized fashion
- Accompanied by statements of proof (e.g., certificates or signatures), making them cryptographically trustworthy

The exchange format for Self-Descriptions is JSON-LD. JSON-LD uses JSON encoding to represent subject-predicate-object triples according to the W3C Resource Description Framework (RDF). The relations between Self-Descriptions form a graph with typed edges, which is called the Self-Description Graph. The Catalogues implement a query algorithm on top of the Self-Description Graph [4].

To foster interoperability, Self-Description schemas with optional and mandatory properties and relations are defined. A Self-Description has to state which schemas are used in its metadata. A Self-Description schema corresponds to a class in RDF. The Self-Description schemas form an extensible class hierarchy with inheritance [12].